

National Open Access Monitor Advisory Group Meeting, 24th January 2023

Present:

- Advisory Group: Fran Callaghan (MU); Caleb Derven (UL); Eoin Kenny (HEAnet); Kevin Kiely (TCD); Andrew Simpson (RCSI).
- IReL: Susan Reilly (Chair); Catherine Ferris (Project Manager); Aaron Binchy (Minutes)

Agenda: Review of “National Open Access Monitor Survey: Defining Requirements”.

Recommendations:

- All agreed for the survey to go out.
- SR and CF to identify a new member to be appointed to the group (from a funder), to replace Hugh Murphy.

Actions:

- CF: Material to be disseminated, outside the survey, of value to wider audience
- CF: Insert structure into start of document indicating that future requirements are invited at the end of the survey
- EK will fill out survey and report back how long it takes to complete, and will provide feedback to Catherine (how long survey takes)
- All: Members to distribute survey to relevant people and groups (identify who to send it to). Send list of any people or groups who should be contacted to CF
- CF to make the following changes to the survey text:
 - Introduction, paragraph 2: “Contributions will be actioned upon from 1st March 2023.”
 - Q.6 a: “When collating and reporting on responses, similar organisations/entities/groups may be grouped together. Please indicate how best to categorise your organisation/entity/group, for this purpose”: fix typo of similar + bold second “organisation/entity/group”.
 - Q.6 a i: “It is acknowledged that organisations/groups/entities perform ranges of activities, and therefore your contribution to this survey may best be represented by another category. If applicable, please indicate below.”: bold “your contribution”.
 - Q.47 “Please indicate which number (#) success criteria in the table above best applies to your organisation/entity/group. Select all that apply.”: change “best applies” to “best apply”
 - Q.51: “Please indicate which User Persona best describes you and/or the users of the National Open Access Monitor from your organisation/entity/group. Select all that apply.”: change “persona” to “personas”

- Q.56: “Please indicate which User Story best applies to your organisation/entity/group. Select all that apply.” change “story” to “stories”
- “Functional Requirements” introduction: insert reference to “Future Functional Requirements” section.
- Q.62, 63, 73, 74: insert additional metric fields
- CF to circulate dates for the next meeting in March